

Investigation and validation of climate data timeseries as derived by ERA5 and ERA20c models and local observations for Kotili, Kastoria, Greece.

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Abstract: We used modeled data from ERA5 and ERA20c models to reconstruct the climate conditions, of the now abandoned village of Kotili, in relation with new on-site observational data. In order, to describe the climate conditions of the last 120 years, that are needed, in further ecological and historical studies. Due to the lack of previous observations, we installed a small weather station and an array of temperature and humidity sensors in the region. By comparing the measured data, from our sensors in the area, we concluded that the modeled data are in good agreement with the observations. These results, indicate a good correlation of the measured parameters with the models, without the need of further adjustments. This approach, establish that the modeled data used, is a viable method for creating a ‘best approximation’ timeseries describing the climatic conditions of this remote location.

1 Introduction

Our goal is to evaluate the feasibility of using past weather modeled data, to reconstruct part of the climatic history of this remote region. The recreated timeseries of climatic data can be correlated with the ecological and cultural history of the region for the last century. The studied region is, the now abandoned village of Kotili (“Παλιά Κοτύλη”) of the prefecture of Kastoria, Greece. A major hinder on establishing the validity of the modeled data was the sparseness of meteorological observations, which coincides with the remoteness of area, the low population density and the distance of other cities. Thus, we installed a small meteorological station and an array of temperature and humidity sensors, in order to obtain on site data. The observations will be compared with the modeled data, in order to evaluate the models’ ability to describe the climate of the region.

2 Data and Methodology

2.1 Data

The modeled data are a product of the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) and obtained from the ERA5 and ERA20C. ERA5 covers a period from 1979 until today, with a spatial resolution of 31 km and temporal resolution of one hour. And similar, the ERA20C spans from 1900 to 2010 with spatial resolution of 0.25° and temporal resolution of six hours.

The observational data obtained by instruments we installed in the region for this purpose, and include a “Davis Vantage Pro2” autonomous weather station and an array of seven “Hobo Pro v2” temperature and humidity loggers. The Davis instrument provided us with measurements of temperature, relative humidity, atmospheric pressure, rainfall, wind speed and wind direction. The instrument took measurements from October 2019 to October 2020, with a time step of two hours. Similar, the Hobo loggers were installed from July 2019 until October 2020 and took measurements every ten minutes. The Davis weather station was placed outside the small narrow valley of the settlement (Fig 1.), in order to be representative of the meteorological conditions for the broader area. The rest of the sensors, were placed at the center of the settlement and at locations where we expected variations due to local conditions. We try to obtain some reference values, from locations near a stream, an open field, inside a forested area, and slopes with different orientation (Fig. 1.).

Fig. 1. Instruments locations, where “HB” one of the HOBO loggers and “DAVIS” the small weather station. The orange line denotes the narrow valley of the old Kotili village (“Κοτύλη Παλιά”).

2.2 Methodology

Due to the lack of other observational data for the location, we are going to use only the data collected by our instruments. At this point, we will focus on the correlation of temperature and relative humidity, as the main indicators of the validity of the modeled data. For the models the relative humidity is computed by the temperature and the dew temperature at the surface, with the following formula.

$$RH\% = 100 * exp\left(17.502\left(\frac{T_{dew} - 273.16}{T_{dew} - 32.16} - \frac{T - 273.16}{T - 32.16}\right)\right)$$

For the geographic location of each sensor, we obtain the corresponding modeled values by bilinear interpolation of the gridded data for each time step. As a result, we produced a time-series of the modeled data which has the same time span as the available modeled data. In order to perform any comparison, we aggregate the measured data, by computing the mean values of each variable, in the time duration that corresponds to the modeled data.

3 Results

Using the matched timeseries of the previous step, we produced correlation statistics between the observations and the ERA5 model (Tables 1 and 2). We provide the relative figures for two of the sensors, for brevity (Fig 2-5).

Table 1. Correlation statistics of **temperature**, between ERA5 model and observations.

Bias	RMSE	IOA	Rsqr	Correlation	N	Name
-2.68	4.28	0.93	0.84	0.92	4574	Davis
-1.62	2.67	0.97	0.94	0.97	10977	HB 1
-1.55	2.7	0.97	0.94	0.97	10977	HB 2
-1.71	2.94	0.97	0.93	0.96	10977	HB 3
-1.57	2.56	0.98	0.95	0.97	10977	HB 4
-3.04	3.96	0.94	0.91	0.96	10977	HB 5
-2.88	4.05	0.94	0.89	0.94	10982	HB 6
-1.99	3.69	0.95	0.87	0.93	10982	HB 7

Table 2. Correlation statistics of **relative humidity**, between ERA5 model and observations.

Bias	RMSE	IOA	Rsqr	Corelation	N	Name
8.28	18.93	0.79	0.44	0.67	4574	Davis
5.72	13.4	0.88	0.69	0.83	10977	HB 1
9.11	15.75	0.84	0.66	0.81	10977	HB 2
8.23	15.72	0.84	0.62	0.79	10977	HB 3
16.04	20.54	0.78	0.66	0.81	10977	HB 4
15.8	21.31	0.77	0.57	0.75	10977	HB 5
12.65	20.05	0.77	0.5	0.71	10982	HB 6
6.63	17.17	0.82	0.5	0.71	10982	HB 7

4 Conclusions

We can determine that there is a satisfactory correlation between the temperatures for all the locations of the sensors, with the model slightly underestimating the actual temperature. In contrast, the correlation for the relative humidity is not as great. This is in part expected, due the attenuation of the variable by the local conditions.

With these finds we feel quite confident, to use the modeled data, in order to construct a timeseries that will describe the climatic conditions of the region for the past century. The lack of meteorological data for longer periods for the area, narrows the validation methods that can be used. As a result, the timeseries from the models have to be used accordingly.

Fig. 2. Temperature correlations of HB 1 sensor and ERA5.

Fig. 3. Relative humidity correlation of HB 1 and ERA5.

Fig. 4. Temperature correlation of HB 1 sensor and Davis station.

Fig. 5. Relative humidity correlation of HB 1 and Davis station.

Acknowledgments: This research has been co-financed by the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH – CREATE – INNOVATE (project code:T1EDK-05225, project title: “Application development for 4D tour in landscape history”).

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